

Evaluation of a RAS facility for Atlantic salmon pathogen research

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What are RAS?

Recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) *or closed containment systems (CCS)*

(shell) fish production units that treat and re-use water

Two distinctive characteristics:

- **Water exchange rate:** water re-use > 90%, nitrate (NO_3) is the controlling parameter.
- **Water treatment units:** mechanical filtration (solids), biofiltration ($\text{NH}_3/\text{NH}_4^+$, NO_2), gas exchange (CO_2)

Biosecurity

High biosecurity, but pathogen breaches are occurring

Example: IPNV, Ca. *Branchiomonas cisticola* and *Yersinia ruckeri*

Infection dynamics in RAS are different: treatment units (biofilter), water re-use and high nutrient availability

Where?

Fish Health laboratory

- Experiments with fish pathogens
- Waste water treatment

Havbruksstasjonen i Tromsø AS
Skarsfjordvegen 860, 9131 Kårvika

Nine replicated RAS

A

RAS

RAS

How was it evaluated

Five independent experimental trials between September 2020 and July 2021

- System description
- Fish parameters variability – Power analysis
- Water quality
- System management metrics
- Disinfection protocol evaluation

Results: fish parameters variability

Fish body weight

Variation within tanks was larger than the variation between tanks

Results: power analysis

Type II: errors fail to reject the null hypothesis when in fact there is a true treatment effect: $b = 20\%$

Objective: to estimate nr of fish need

Results: water quality & system management metrics

TABLE 2 | Water quality and system management metrics for the five experimental trials.

Parameter*	Experiment					CV _{Treat.} (%)	CV _{Exp.} (%)
	1	2	3	4	5		
Water quality in fish tank							
O ₂ (% saturation)	97.1	97.3	94.7	100.2	93.3	1.2	2.7
CO ₂ (mg/L)	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1.3	–	–
pH	6.91	7.27	7.49	7.56	7.17	1.6	3.6
Temperature (C°)	12.7	12.6	12.7	12.6	12.2	1.0	1.7
Turbidity (NTU)	2.67	1.11	0.79	0.67	6.95	35.0	108.6
NH ₄ -N (mg/L)	0.06	0.05	5.67	2.48	0.08	45.4	148.1
NH ₃ -N (μg/L)	0.10	0.20	38.49	19.52	0.26	49.4	146.4
NO ₂ -N (mg/L)	0.03	0.03	0.05	2.69	0.11	60.0	202.6
NO ₃ -N (mg/L)	3.07	2.74	0.49	3.17	12.2	21.1	104.6
System management metrics							
Maximum fish density (kg/m ³)	0.6	0.6	1.1	1.5	5.9	13.5	115.8
Mean hydraulic retention time (HRT)							
Fish tank (min)	20	20	30	20	20	0	20.3
System (h)	11.7	13.0	10.9	8.2	2.0	17.2	47.7
System water exchange rate (%volume/d)	3.5	3.2	4.2	5.0	19.7	19.6	99.3
Water exchange rate (L/kg feed)	985	961	1,213	1,579	687	19.6	30.7
Make-up water (L/min./ kg fish)	2.6	2.2	1.6	1.4	1.3	25.1	30.7

**Low variation
Sensor
controlled**

Results: water quality & system management metrics

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**High variation
BIO/Operator
controlled**

Results: disinfection protocol evaluation

Protocol: surface cleaning w/ alkaline hypochlorite-containing detergent

Protocol tested:

Results: disinfection protocol evaluation

Protocol: surface cleaning w/ alkaline hypochlorite-containing detergent

Protocol tested:

Take-home message

Test and evaluate your RAS units

Valuable information on:

- System description
- Fish parameters variability – Power analysis
- Water quality & system management metrics
- Disinfection protocol evaluation

Evaluation of a Recirculating Aquaculture System Research Facility Designed to Address Current Knowledge Needs in Atlantic Salmon Production

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Thank you for
your attention!

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